

Parameters affecting the precipitation of Al-phases from aluminate solutions of the Pedersen process

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Abstract

A theoretical thermodynamic study of a sodium aluminate solution originating from the Na₂CO₃ leaching of a calcium aluminate slag was conducted to specify the thermodynamically favoured species that exist within. Using the HSC 9.0 software, a carbonation process (neutralisation of the aluminate solution with CO₂ gas) was simulated in order to assess the thermodynamically favoured solid phases that precipitate. Laboratory carbonation experiments were conducted to verify the theoretical predictions. According to the theoretical study, at temperatures below 50 °C gibbsite precipitates in the first 20 minutes of the process and then is transformed to dawsonite. Temperatures over 65 °C favour the direct precipitation of dawsonite. The experimental work verified the latter observation but not the former.

Introduction

The Pedersen process is a process aiming at the production of cast iron and metallurgical alumina from bauxites and other Al-containing resources¹. Originally applied in industrial scale in Norway until 1969, it consisted of two stages. The first stage is a reductive smelting of bauxite with lime, leading to the production of metallic iron and a calcium aluminate (CA) slag. In the second stage the CA slag is hydrometallurgically treated with a Na₂CO₃ solution, a process leading, in principle, to the extraction of Al in the PLS and a calcium carbonate residue. The PLS is then neutralized with CO₂ gas (carbonation process), leading to the precipitation of alumina trihydrate, suitable for producing metallurgical alumina. Studying the process from a 21st century perspective certain attractive features stand out. Firstly, it promises a complete utilisation of bauxite ores, even some rejected by the Bayer Process². Moreover, the hydrometallurgical conditions applied are moderate and, most importantly, the issue of bauxite residue is eliminated as, in its place, a calcium-based residue is produced.

The focus of the current work is the link between the leaching and the precipitation operations of the hydrometallurgical side of the Pedersen process.

Initially, after performing leaching tests in a CA slag of modelled composition, a PLS of chosen composition was selected on the basis of maximum dissolved Al. A thermodynamic analysis was performed with the software HSC 9.0 to assess the phases predicted to precipitate from such solutions under a carbonation process similar to the original Pedersen Process. Afterwards experiments were performed to confirm the thermodynamic predictions.

Materials and Methodology

Leaching tests performed in the Laboratory of Metallurgy of NTUA on a CA slag originating from the reductive smelting of Greek Bauxite suggested that the highest Al_2O_3 extraction was achieved for an aluminate solution of the composition presented in Table 1. This composition was used as the basis for the precipitation experiments.

Table 1. Average compositions of aluminate solutions used in precipitation tests

Species	Concentration	
	g/L	mol/L
Na_2CO_3	160	1.5
NaOH	20	0.5
$\text{NaAl}(\text{OH})_4$	36.0	0.3
Na_2SiO_3	1.2	0.01

For the theoretical analysis of a carbonation process, the HSC 9.0 software was utilized. To model the PLS, the “ideal mixture” solution model was applied. The species considered were as follows: (1) all aluminium aqueous hydroxo-, mono- and poly-nuclear, as well as carbonato- complexes, (2) all sodium species, (3) all silicon species, (4) sodium aluminosilicate phases such as nepheline were considered to simulate Si-undersaturated aluminosilicates, as well as several zeolite compounds such as analcime, natrolite, etc. and (5) carbonated solid phases such as dawsonite $[\text{NaAlCO}_3(\text{OH})_2]$ and cancrisilite. Several species such as hydroxy-sodalite and Na-cancrinite were not considered as they are absent from the software database.

Turning to the experimental verification of the theoretical modelling, all synthetic aluminate solutions for the precipitation tests were prepared with reagent grade NaOH (pellets), Na_2CO_3 (anhydrous powder), $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$ from MYTILINEOS S.A. and SiO_2 (99.5% purity). The reagents are mixed with 400mL of deionized water at 160 °C for 2 h in an autoclave until completely dissolved. The solutions were then transferred to a 500 mL volumetric flask. The precipitation experiments took place in a modified Parr autoclave system, with a specially made Teflon lid. All

experiments were performed under atmospheric pressure condition. For each test, 400 ml of synthetic aluminate solution is introduced into the reactor and heated to the desired temperature. Gas is then introduced at a constant flow (200 cm³/min) controlled by a flowmeter (Omega FMA series). Introducing the gas into the inlet signifies the start of the experiment. pH measurements are taken per minute and the stirring rate remained constant at 150rpm. At the end of each experiment the solution was filtered. Solid phase analysis is performed with XRD or FT-IR.

Results and discussion

Thermodynamic Analysis of PLS

The Al speciation diagram of the PLS can be seen in Figure 1 and it is supersaturated in Al. At temperatures below 50 °C, gibbsite is spontaneously precipitated, whereas at temperatures over 65 °C, dawsonite is spontaneously precipitated. This phenomenon can be attributed to the values of K_{sp} of both solids at different temperatures. As it can be seen in Figure 2, at temperatures below 50 °C, the K_{sp} of gibbsite is lower than that of dawsonite.

Figure 1. Aluminum speciation diagram of PLS used in this study.

Figure 2. Solubility product constant (K_{sp}) of aluminum hydroxide ($\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$) and dawsonite $\text{NaAlCO}_3(\text{OH})_2$ versus temperature

Over 65 °C values are reversed. The prediction that these two phases can precipitate out of the PLS at different temperatures formed the backbone for the simulation in HSC 9.0. To be more precise, carbonation was studied for two temperature values, one below 50 °C and one over 65 °C. The values chosen were 40 °C and 80 °C, respectively.

Carbonation study of PLS at 80 °C

To simulate the precipitation mechanism with carbon dioxide gas (CO₂) injection in HSC 9.0, the software was programmed to simulate a stepwise insertion of the gas. The results of the simulation are depicted as speciation diagrams for the elements of interest, i.e. Al, Na and Si. As it can be seen in the Al speciation diagram (Figure 3), at 80 °C the main precipitate is dawsonite. This can be attributed to the degree of Al supersaturation, as well as to the high free carbonate ion content of the PLS. In the Na speciation diagram (Figure 4), it is shown that carbonation of more than 110 minutes leads to removal of Na as Na₂CO₃·NaHCO₃·2H₂O and NaHCO₃. Finally, the speciation diagram of Si (Figure 5) shows that at pH≈11 about 73% of Si is precipitated in the form of natrolite.

Figure 3. Al speciation diagram of precipitates at 80 °C with 200 ml/min CO₂ injection

Figure 4. Na speciation diagram of precipitates at 80 °C with 200 ml/min CO₂ injection

Figure 5. Si speciation diagram of precipitates at 80 °C with 200 ml/min CO₂ injection

Carbonation study of PLS at 40 °C

For the simulation at 40 °C with HSC 9.0 the same commands were used as with the simulation at 80 °C. It can be observed in the Al speciation diagram of Figure 6 that Al(OH)₃ is initially precipitated but, with the progression of carbonation, it transforms to dawsonite. Figure 7 reveals that in the first 20 minutes of carbonation Na₂CO₃·7H₂O is precipitated along with gibbsite and for a duration of more than 95 minutes soda is removed as NaHCO₃. Finally, as expected, Si is being precipitated in the form of natrolite to an extent of 83%.

Figure 6. Al speciation diagram of precipitates at 80 °C with 200 ml/min CO₂ injection

Figure 7. Na speciation diagram of precipitates at 80 °C with 200 ml/min CO₂ injection

Experimental verification of carbonation study

For the 80 °C simulation the experimental conditions were as follows: 200 ml/min CO₂ addition, 130 minutes CO₂ purging and no aging. The pH records can be seen at Figure 8a, where a sharp drop of pH is observed in the first 12 minutes (from 11.2 to 10.13). Then the pH is gradually lowered until a value of about 8.6 and then remains stable. Figure 8b presents the XRD analysis of the precipitate which shows that dawsonite is formed as the thermodynamic analysis had predicted. AAS

analysis of the remaining solution after precipitation shows that 100% of Al is precipitated and 59.8% of Si.

For the 40 °C simulation the experimental conditions were as follows: 200 ml/min CO₂ addition, 20 minutes CO₂ purging and 60 minutes aging time. Figure 9a depicts the pH records during the experiment. The amount of the precipitate was exceptionally small and XRD analysis could not be conducted. Thus, FTIR analysis is presented in Figure 9b, which shows that the main phase is dawsonite. This result indicates either that for kinetic reasons gibbsite is never formed or that the theoretical modelling needs improvement.

Figure 8. Carbonation experiment at 80 °C (a) pH vs T and (b) XRD of precipitate.

Figure 9. Carbonation at 40 °C, (a) pH vs T and (b) FTIR of precipitate

Conclusions

A theoretical modelling of an aluminate PLS, originating from calcium aluminate slag leaching with Na₂CO₃, showed that gibbsite is spontaneously precipitated below 65 °C and dawsonite over 65 °C. Modelling a carbonation process for PLS showed that at 80 °C, dawsonite is instantly precipitated, which was also proven experimentally. At 40 °C, according to the thermodynamic modelling of the carbonation, gibbsite should initially precipitate. The experiments though showed that only dawsonite is precipitated, suggesting that further work is needed to define the conditions suitable for gibbsite precipitation.

Acknowledgements

“This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 767533. This publication reflects only the author's view, exempting the Community from any liability”. Project web site: <https://www.ensureal.com/>

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